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Pronunciation Teaching Strategies

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Abstract

The aim of this lesson is to provide a teacher with strategies that are suitable for use in pronunciation learning. And this is very useful for students and teachers. In Indonesia there are still many who have difficulty learning pronunciation. This happens because teachers cannot understand learning strategies, especially in the pronunciation section. In Indonesia, strategies must be implemented on how to teach easy pronunciation to provide understanding to students. Improving English pronunciation is a crucial goal for many Indonesian learners, as it directly impacts their ability to communicate effectively in a global context. This article has outlined a range of evidence-based strategies that can be employed to enhance pronunciation instruction in the Indonesian classroom. From explicit instruction on English sounds and sound patterns to the integration of pronunciation practice within communicative activities, these strategies aim to address the unique challenges faced by Indonesian learners. The use of multimodal approaches, personalized feedback, and the creation of a positive learning environment further contribute to the effectiveness of pronunciation teaching. By implementing these strategies, teachers in Indonesia can help their students develop more accurate, intelligible, and confident pronunciation skills, empowering them to engage in meaningful and successful communication in English.

Keywords: *Pronunciation, teaching, strategies*

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INTRODUCTION

The aim of this lesson is to provide a teacher with strategies that are suitable for use in pronunciation learning. And this is very useful for students and teachers. In Indonesia there are still many who have difficulty learning pronunciation. This happens because teachers cannot understand learning strategies, especially in the pronunciation section. In Indonesia, strategies must be implemented on how to teach easy pronunciation to provide understanding to students.

Since humans are social creatures, communication is the most crucial aspect of existence. Everyone uses communication as a means of interacting with people in social situations. A successful communication process depends on mutual understanding between the sender and the recipient. As a result, effective communication requires effective communication skills (Umara & Lestari, 2020). In communication, people should have good pronunciation in order to understand each other. One of the key components of learning English is pronunciation, which helps the speaker communicate more effectively. When communication occurs, mispronounced words create confusion, misunderstandings, and alternative meanings (Khoiriyah, 2020). Good pronunciation can achieve the goal of becoming an understandable speaker. Good pronunciation also will clearly carry out the oral skills required for information estimation. Furthermore, anticipate that others will comprehend what we are truly trying to express in addition to us concentrating just on the information we wish to convey (Dheghu, Mata, & Rita, 2021).

English is not the native tongue in Indonesia; it is a foreign language. The study of pronunciation, one of the components of learning English, has grown in importance in the context of teaching English to speakers of other languages. According to Goodwin (2011:117), the purpose of pronunciation instruction is threefold: (1) to help students understand and be understood; (2) to increase their self-assurance when engaging in communication; and (3) to help students monitor their speech in response to environmental cues. The comment demonstrated the importance of pronunciation in teaching English to non-native speakers (Darmawan & Prischilla, 2019).

This strategy is really needed for teachers and instructors. Here I will research the strategies needed to learn about pronunciation in the classroom in order to reduce this problem in Indonesia. You

will also gain proficiency in pronunciation because it is really needed among teachers and students.

Reading aloud can help develop linguistic reflexes, help the tongue respond to new sound combinations, and acclimate the brain to word patterns, according to Scola (2009:16). As a result, through reading aloud, the students would learn how to make the proper English sounds, and the researcher would be able to quickly determine whether or not the students' sounds were correct. Reading aloud can also assist those students who lacked the confidence to practice speaking English in public.

The aim of learning English in Indonesia is more than just linguistic competence; it is related to broader educational goals which aim to develop global competence, socio-cultural awareness and economic foreign power. Based on the explanation that has been explained, researchers are interested in learning more about strategies for learning English pronunciation in Indonesia, so the formulation of the question to be presented in this research is "What are the strategies for learning English pronunciation in Indonesia properly and correctly?"

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Integrating Pronunciation with Communicative Activities

While explicit instruction on English sounds and sound patterns is essential, it is equally important to integrate pronunciation practice within meaningful, communicative activities. This approach helps learners apply their newly acquired pronunciation skills in real-life, context-embedded scenarios, rather than in isolation. One effective strategy is to incorporate pronunciation work into task-based or project-based learning activities (Riskiwati, 2022:8). For instance, students can be asked to prepare and deliver a short presentation on a topic of their choice, with a focus on using proper pronunciation, stress, and intonation patterns. Alternatively, learners can engage in role-play exercises or discussions that require them to negotiate meaning and maintain clear communication, thereby highlighting the importance of accurate pronunciation.

By integrating pronunciation practice into communicative tasks, teachers can help students develop a stronger understanding of how pronunciation affects overall comprehensibility and intelligibility. This, in turn, can motivate learners to pay closer attention to their pronunciation and strive for continuous improvement. Furthermore, the use of authentic, real-world materials, such as news broadcasts, podcasts, or TV shows, can provide valuable exposure to natural, native-like pronunciation models. Students can then engage in shadowing or repetition exercises to mimic the target sounds and patterns, gradually building their confidence and fluency.

Multimodal Approaches to Pronunciation Instruction

To cater to the diverse learning styles and needs of Indonesian students, it is beneficial to employ a multimodal approach to pronunciation instruction. This involves the integration of various sensory inputs and teaching techniques to enhance the learners' understanding and retention of pronunciation skills. One effective multimodal strategy is the use of visual aids, such as articulatory diagrams, mouth and lip position illustrations, and sound-color associations (color-coding vowel sounds) (Kusuma, 2021:264). These visual representations can help students develop a better understanding of the physical mechanics of sound production, as well as the unique features of English pronunciation. Additionally, the incorporation of kinesthetic and tactile activities can further reinforce pronunciation learning. For example, students can be encouraged to use their hands to feel the vibrations of their vocal cords during the production of voiced and voiceless sounds, or to observe and mimic the lip and tongue movements of the teacher or a native speaker. Another multimodal approach is the integration of technology-assisted pronunciation training. This can include the use of speech recognition software, audio/video recordings, and interactive pronunciation apps or websites. These technological tools can provide learners with immediate feedback on their pronunciation, as well as opportunities for self-assessment and personalized practice. By catering to multiple sensory modalities, teachers can enhance the effectiveness of pronunciation instruction and cater to the diverse learning needs of their Indonesian students. This multifaceted approach can lead to improved retention, increased engagement, and better overall pronunciation outcomes.

Personalized Feedback and Error Correction

Strategies Providing learners with personalized feedback and effective error correction strategies is crucial for improving their pronunciation skills. Teachers should carefully observe and analyze their students' pronunciation patterns, identifying both strengths and areas for improvement.

One effective approach is to use a combination of implicit and explicit error correction techniques. Implicit feedback, such as recasts or clarification requests, can help students notice and self-correct their pronunciation errors without disrupting the flow of communication. Explicit feedback, on the other hand, involves directly highlighting the error and providing the correct model or explanation. For example, when a student mispronounces a word, the teacher can respond with a recast, such as: "Ah, I see. So, the word is 'computer,' not 'computa.'" This allows the student to recognize the error and immediately hear the correct pronunciation. Alternatively, the teacher can provide more explicit feedback, saying: "The 'r' sound at the end of 'computer' is important. Let's practice that one more time." Additionally, teachers can incorporate peer-feedback activities, where students work in pairs or small groups to listen to and provide constructive feedback on each other's pronunciation (Tan, 2021:256). This not only helps learners identify their own weaknesses but also fosters a supportive and collaborative learning environment. By delivering personalized, targeted feedback and employing a range of error correction strategies, teachers can help Indonesian students develop a stronger awareness of their pronunciation strengths and weaknesses, ultimately leading to more consistent and accurate production of English sounds and patterns.

Fostering a Positive and Supportive Learning Environment

Creating a positive and supportive learning environment is essential for helping Indonesian students overcome their fears and anxieties related to pronunciation practice. Many learners may feel self-conscious or reluctant to actively participate in pronunciation activities, especially in front of their peers. To address this challenge, teachers should strive to cultivate a classroom atmosphere that is encouraging, non-judgmental, and focused on progress rather than perfection. This can be achieved through various strategies, such as: Emphasizing the importance of risk-taking and making mistakes as part of the learning process. Providing frequent positive reinforcement and constructive feedback to boost students' confidence and motivation (Rusnaini, 2020:12). Encouraging peer support and collaborative learning, where students can practice pronunciation in a safe and supportive environment. Incorporating fun, engaging, and low-stress pronunciation activities, such as tongue twisters, songs, or games. Recognizing and celebrating small achievements and milestones in pronunciation development. By fostering a supportive and inclusive learning environment, teachers can help Indonesian students feel more comfortable and confident in their pronunciation practice, ultimately leading to greater progress and sustained motivation.

CONCLUSION

Improving English pronunciation is a crucial goal for many Indonesian learners, as it directly impacts their ability to communicate effectively in a global context. This article has outlined a range of evidence-based strategies that can be employed to enhance pronunciation instruction in the Indonesian classroom. From explicit instruction on English sounds and sound patterns to the integration of pronunciation practice within communicative activities, these strategies aim to address the unique challenges faced by Indonesian learners. The use of multimodal approaches, personalized feedback, and the creation of a positive learning environment further contribute to the effectiveness of pronunciation teaching. By implementing these strategies, teachers in Indonesia can help their students develop more accurate, intelligible, and confident pronunciation skills, empowering them to engage in meaningful and successful communication in English. As students continue to improve their pronunciation, they will not only enhance their language proficiency but also gain valuable intercultural competence, crucial for navigating the increasingly interconnected global landscape.

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